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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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DEVELOPMENT OF A SET OF HEALTH-PROMOTING EXERCISES FOR MIDDLE-AGED MEN 50-60 YEARS OLD, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT PHYSICAL TRAINING

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Abstract: This article discusses the development of a set of health-improving exercises for middle-aged men aged 45-60, taking into account physical fitness. There are also statistics on the incidence and risk factors for middle-aged men aged 50-60 years. Specialized programs of rehabilitation and preventive exercises for men using simulators have been developed and tested, which have proven their effectiveness.

Key words: health, exercise, physical performance, quality of life, morbidity rate, prevention, exercise, simulator.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada o`rta yoshdagi 50-60 yoshli erkaklar uchun jismoniy tayyorgarlikni hisobga olgan holda sog`lomlashtiruvchi mashqlar jamlanmasini ishlab chiqish haqida so`z yuritilgan. Shuningdek, o`rta yoshdagi 50-60 yoshli erkaklarning kasallanish darajasi va kasallanish uchun xavf omillari bo`yicha statistik ma`lumotlar keltirilgan. Simulyatorlardan foydalangan holda erkaklar uchun sog`lomlashtiruvchi va profilaktika mashqlarining ixtisoslashtirilgan dasturlari ishlab chiqilgan va sinovdan o`tgan bo`lib, ular samaradorligini isbotlandi.

Kalit so`zlar: sog`liqni saqlash, mashg`ulotlar, jismoniy ko`rsatkichlar, hayot sifati, kasallanish darajasi, profilaktika, mashq, simulyator.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается разработка комплекса оздоровительных упражнений для мужчин среднего возраста 50-60 лет с учетом физической подготовленности. Имеются также статистические данные о заболеваемости и факторах риска для мужчин среднего возраста в возрасте 50-60 лет. Разработаны и апробированы специализированные программы реабилитационных и профилактических упражнений для мужчин с использованием тренажеров, доказавшие свою эффективность.

Ключевые слова: здоровье, физические упражнения, физическая работоспособность, качество жизни, заболеваемость, профилактика, физические упражнения, тренажер.

INTRODUCTION

Technological advances have affected all areas of activity. With the advent of smartphones, computers and other devices, these devices have become part of our way of life. Doing daily chores has become much easier. This has led to a sharp decline in a person's physical activity. This process has a negative impact on functional abilities, as well as weakens the human musculoskeletal system. The whole body changed its function, but, unfortunately, the changes were not positive, but negative. Due to the minimization of movement, a sharp decrease in energy consumption leads to damage to the muscles, heart, blood vessels and respiratory system. All this affects the body and health, leading to the development of many diseases. Sports activities shortages and shortages also have an impact on the energy distribution system. Moreover, in the realities of our time, it is sports and physical education that have become the only way to perform activities that allow any person to meet their natural need for a certain amount of load and movement.

Consistent measures are being taken in our country to promote physical culture and sports, create the necessary conditions and infrastructure to promote a healthy lifestyle, especially among young people, to ensure the country's worthy participation in international sports arenas. At the same time, the existence of a number of systemic problems and shortcomings in the organization of physical culture and sports makes public policy in this area effective and make full use of the country's existing sporting potential.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As evidenced by the results of studies in recent years, middle-aged people have a significant decrease in the level of somatic health and physical fitness, deterioration of the functional and often, psycho-emotional state. In the same time. It has been proved that, under the condition of regular physical exercises, to the maximum extent corresponding to the state of health and characteristics of the organism of those involved, persons of the second period of mature age can demonstrate a level of psychophysical condition close to that of young healthy people who have not crossed the 30 year mark.

Objective of the study was to study the effects of the specially designed healthimproving training program on the 50-60 year-old males who are at risk of formation of cardiovascular diseases.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out at the premises of the (Tashkent region) and involved 30 males aged 50-60 years, who were divided into the Control and Experimental Groups, 15 people each. All men were not diagnosed with cardiovascular diseases but were at risk of their formation.

During the study, we developed the training programs (health-improving training No.1a (1st semester), health-improving training No.1b (2nd semester) for this population category and assessed its effectiveness. The Control Group subjects were trained according to the standard program in the gym: 3-4 training sessions per week, 50-60 min each. The Experimental Group subjects were trained under the training program health-improving training No.1a, which was based on the developing (in the 1st half of the academic year) and training (in the 2nd half of the academic year) motor modes. They practiced 3-4 times per week for 50-60 min throughout the year.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The effectiveness of the versatile healthimproving training programs is confirmed by the increase in the endurance rate in the Experimental Group by 10% versus the Control Group, as well as by the improvement in the quality of life of this population category and by their widespread introduction into the practice of physical education and fitness activities.

It becomes relevant, as with the appearance of the first threats health and to delay the formation of age-related pathology and disability. Meanwhile, an effective increase in the functional capabilities of the circulatory system and an increase in exercise tolerance in middle-aged and elderly people, even with coronary heart disease, during physical exercises according to an individual program of physical cardiorehabilitation have been proven ^[1].

Despite the downward trend in recent years of diseases of the respiratory, digestive and genitourinary systems, there has been a noticeable increase over the past decade by 1.4% in the proportion of diseases of the circulatory system ^[2]. Moreover, the mortality statistics for men aged 45–60 proves that, in comparison with women at this age, it is 3.1 times higher.

A significant reduction in the scale of the personnel crisis in the country could be facilitated not only by medical, but also by health-improving and preventive measures with an emphasis on strengthening these systems of the body of older people, which together are capable of returning up to 850 thousand workers a year.

A 2002 WHO report noted that more than 20% of cases. The development of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) in developed countries is due to low levels of physical activity. Therefore, physical exercises are included in the complex program of physical rehabilitation for various age-related pathologies. So, among the positive effects of physical training of middle-aged and elderly people under the cardiorehabilitation program, positive changes important for the elderly are reliably noted: reduction in overall mortality by 20% (including CVD mortality by 26%); improvement of functionality (increase in oxygen consumption, increase in cardiac output, decrease in systemic vascular resistance, myocardial remodeling after myocardial infarction, improvement in systolic function of the left ventricle of the heart, increase in exercise tolerance) ^[1].

In the course of the experiment with men aged 45–60, the most effective forms of health-improving physical culture were proven. However, studies by physiologists show that in mature (≥ 50 years old) and elderly people, the process of forming new motor skills slows down; difficult to carry out various game techniques, complex-coordinated movements, physical exercises at a fast pace; speed, flexibility, agility, muscle strength, physical performance decrease, the physiological cost of the work performed increases, but at the same time endurance remains stable and stereotypes of labor (trained) skills are preserved ^[4].

Analysis of demographic processes in the subsidized Tashkent region showed that the number of labor resources over the past 15 years has decreased by 4.2%. Both in Uzbekistan as a whole and in the Tashkent region, the leading cause of disability at the age of 50–59 years is diseases of the circulatory system (75%). The second place among the causes of disability in the Uzbekistan among the population at the specified age is occupied by malignant neoplasms (17%). In the Smolensk region, the maximum level of cases of neoplasms was noted both in working age (5.2 cases per 10 thousand population) and in retirement age (29.3 cases per 10,000 population), with lung cancer in first place in men, and stomach cancer in second place. Prostate cancer also deserves attention, the growth of which is increasing every year ^[3].

Results of the study and their discussion. For students of the 1st and 2nd groups, the average annual score on the IFS scale was 4.46 ± 0.04 and 4.39 ± 0.071 points, respectively, which characterized by good physical condition, high level of health and performance reserves. Wherein the estimated result of the 3rd group was lower and amounted to 4.15 ± 0.01 points ($p < 0.001$).

It should be noted that FSI values are subject to seasonal fluctuations. The examination of a group of female students in the spring of 2019 was marked by the maximum values of the FSI in all the examined. In autumn, the FSI index in the 1st group was 4.34 ± 0.018 ; 2nd - 4.32 ± 0.019 , in the 3rd - 4.19 ± 0.03 points. Reliably low indices of the index were noted in winter and amounted to: in the 1st - 4.3 ± 0.02 , in the 2nd - 4.24 ± 0.03 , in the 3rd - 4.02 ± 0.07 points.

Seasonal dynamics of body weight and BMI in all surveyed is characterized by higher values in winter, which is associated with a decrease in motor activity and metabolic changes during this period. It was revealed that female students involved in the “Fitness yoga” groups have higher average annual values of physiological indicators. Output. The value of the index of physical condition is significantly higher among female students of the “Fitness Yoga” group than among girls studying under the OFP program, regardless of seasons of the year. This indicates the effectiveness of this form of training and allows us to recommend the introduction type of health-improving classes of the specialization “Fitnessyoga” in the educational process within the framework of the PFP of the university.

Based on the data of the ascertaining experiment, theoretically, two specialized programs of health-improving and preventive exercises were developed using simulators, including exercises of general and special orientation (for the respiratory muscles, abdominal muscles, pelvic floor), as well as cyclic exercises of an aerobic nature, moderate intensity (Table 2). The comprehensive OT program No. 1, designed for men with a moderate risk of a decline in health, is based on a training motor regimen and included exercises on the Cardio Twister simulator, performed at an average pace and cyclic exercises at a pace of 70-100 steps / min (health walking, park orientation, close tourism). Given that with age, not only the proportion of people with poor adaptation from various body systems associated with general age-related changes (overweight, metabolic disorders, atherosclerosis, varicose symptom complex, coronary artery disease, genitourinary dysfunctions) increases, the peculiarity of health-improving and preventive exercises men 45–60 years old is regular physical activity of an aerobic nature is moderate.

CONCLUSIONS

1. As a result of the analysis of the incidence of the population in Uzbekistan, priority diseases were identified by systems, resulting in early death or disability of men over 50 years of age: in I place - diseases of the circulatory system, in II place - diseases of the respiratory system and neoplasms, in III place – disease digestive and urinary systems.
2. Typical age-related risk factors among men, living in subsidized regions are smoking - 83.3%, malnutrition and low medical activity - 86.6% and physical inactivity - 91.7%, which necessitate the development and implementation of organized gender-age fitness programs in order to modify age-related risk factors in men over 50 years of age.
3. The effectiveness of variable health training programs has been practically proven, which is confirmed by a significant increase in motivation for physical exercises by 40.3%, physical performance - by 1.2 times ($p \leq 0.01$), the quality of life indicator for men - by 1.3 times ($p \leq 0.01$) and an increase in working capacity by 16.6%. This program can be introduced into the practice of health-improving and preventive measures for men over 50 years of age.

All of us have come to the serious conclusion that it is necessary to give up harmful habits, to engage in mass sports, to follow the principles of proper nutrition, in particular, to eat pastries and sweets that are high in salt, sugar and fat. We need to understand that today's era itself requires us not to overeat bread, in short, to make a healthy lifestyle our daily life.

Regular physical activity and mass sports, as well as the formation of life skills for a healthy lifestyle, will help every citizen to fight the disease to develop a strong immune system, to give up bad habits, to follow the principles of proper nutrition, rehabilitation and rehabilitation, as well as mass physical activity.

In order to organize systematic and effective activities, to create the appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions, everyone should lead a healthy lifestyle and seek solutions to the further development of mass sports.

References:

1. Гилев Г.А. Физическая культура в вузе – средство социальной защиты студенчества // Матер. междунар. науч.-практ. конф. “Актуальные проблемы сохранения и укрепления здоровья молодежи Сибирского региона”. – Иркутск. – 2006. – С.8-9.
2. Andris E. Kudratov R. Athletics. - T., 1998.
3. Normurodov A. Athletics. - 2. T., 2002.
4. Niyozov I. Athletics. -Ferghana, 2005.
5. Matveev L.P. Theory and methods of physical culture M.1991.
6. Abdullaev A., Xonkeldiev Sh. Theory and methods of physical education T, 2005.
7. Sports newspapers. 1992-2005
8. A.Normurodov, Physical training 1998

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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